

An Analysis of Biometric Devices to Deter Criminal Activities in the University of Limpopo

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The purpose of this paper is to assess the implementation of biometric systems in the University of Limpopo to prevent criminal activities. It argues that the University of Limpopo is one of the Universities that has been using old technology, especially to control the movement of people from the gates and the university residences. This article seeks to demonstrate the need for and implementation of biometric systems as one of the latest technological innovations, which is compatible with the 4IR. Although there is a significant headway in terms of the implementation of the biometric system, much more still needs to be done. This article is established on the basis that non-students also enter the university premises illegally because the system of control at the gates is poor and vulnerable to criminal syndicates. At times, students and to some extent, staff members would lend student/staff cards to their accomplices who are not students to enter the university. This already threatens the lives of students and staff on the university premises. This is a conceptual paper that relies on the use of secondary data. It finds that the application of biometrics for crime prevention and control has garnered notable interest with the progression of technology. Biometrics involves the distinctive physiological or behavioural traits possessed by individuals, which can be employed for purposes of identification and verification. These traits encompass fingerprints, facial recognition, iris scans, voice identification and even DNA analysis.

Keywords: Biometric devices, criminal activities, technology, University of Limpopo

Governments, the private sector and to a larger extent, universities are increasingly employing biometric devices to deter and resolve criminal activities. Clark (2022) contends that biometric technologies like fingerprinting, Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) analysis, and facial recognition have demonstrated their effectiveness as dependable tools in the battle against crime. This paper delves into and critiques the current University of Limpopo biometric systems at the gates. The entrance gates of universities experience significant surges in activity during two primary peak periods: one occurring in the morning and the other in the evening, aligning with the university's work schedule (Al-Omari, Al-Omari, & Shdifat, 2019). This situation has the potential to lead to congestion during these specific timeframes. A well-thought-out entrance and exit biometric system design should avert the formation of car queues, as these lined-up vehicles obstruct and disrupt the flow of traffic on the nearby street. Optimal selection of the number of biometric devices such as facial recognition, fingerprints and hand-scanning amongst others, contributes to the smooth functioning of entrances and exits, resulting in minimal instances of criminal-related issues (Frantzeskakis, 1981). Entrances and exits, commonly

referred to as gates, hold significant importance within the transportation infrastructure as they serve as crucial points of separation between external road networks and the internal roadways of various facilities (Fussey & Murray, 2019).

Security plays a crucial role in the life of the nation when it comes to establishing an authoritative institution. The issue of criminal activity is pervasive in modern culture and society, with unacceptable levels of crime present in the majority of countries (Anderez, Kanjo, Anwar, Johnson, & Lucy, 2021). The rate at which crime is increasing is quite shocking and keeps on increasing on a daily especially in our country, South Africa. According to the annual Performance Plan (2025/2026) from the office of the Chief Justice, South Africa has the third- highest crime rate in the world being 76.86%. With more and more levels of crime increasing, South Africa is at risk of being in danger. However, biometric technology is quickly becoming a key component of real life in the twenty-first century as one of the key factors of crime control and crime prevention strategies. Biometrics are used in areas as diverse as security for business, school, government agencies, borders and airports; patient identification in hospitals and blood banks; voice control of electronic devices; and criminal investigations (Trader, 2014; Gray, 2019). However, people may think of biometrics in terms of face recognition; there are many other types of biometrics in use or in development as well, such as voice and iris recognition. In this new generation of moving into the 4IR, it is demonstrated in both public and private institutions all over the world to deter any crime issues from occurring as one of the most fascinating uses of biometrics (Jansen, Sacher-Monedero, & Denrick, 2021). Biometrics are widely utilized by government and commercial organizations around the world for purposes such as border control, law enforcement, as well as forensic investigations (Drozdowski, Rathgeb, Dantcheva, Damer, & Christoph, 2020).

In countries such as the United Kingdom (UK), United States

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of America (USA) and Australia, the use of technology and its application has been widely debated, as biometric technology is one of the significant and rapidly developing Artificial Intelligence (AI) currently available for security and law enforcement purposes (Smith & Miller, 2021). Europe indicates that the use of bodily characteristics such as face, irises or retina for governing is becoming prevalent (Fussey & Murray, 2019; Marciano, 2019). The purpose of this paper is to analyse the implementation of biometric devices in deterring criminal activities in the University of Limpopo by focusing on the technical aspect and different biometric devices, looking further into the number of associated issues and current applications of biometric technology.

Research Problem

Crime rates vary greatly from country to country and are influenced by many factors (World Population Review, 2023). For instance, high levels and unemployment tend to inflate a country's crime rate. As more emerging high levels of crime there are, the more they pose a serious threat to the University of Limpopo premises. Not only in the University but also in the world at large, especially in developing countries, such as South Africa. Which is why the paper attempts to ameliorate criminal issues by coming up with the implementation of modern technologies, which is the installation of biometric devices to prevent crime from increasing in the University of Limpopo. Although there is an attempt by the University of Limpopo in implementing innovative biometric systems at the main gates, it is not sufficient because some systems like facial recognition and fingerprints are defunct. The increasing criminal activities discovered in the university are crime such as theft on the campus where students are hijacked of their gadgets, be it phones and laptops, usually at night after library studies, walking to their respective residences. There are some cases of rape, usually at night on campus, whereby some girls are raped and there is also smuggling of unwanted or rather illegal goods such as alcohol, drugs and knives. The smuggling of illegal goods often enters the campus by people without a student card to prove that they are students. As certain people from the community of Mankweng are given a chance to bypass the campus in the form of a shortcut to get to gate 2 from gate. Basically, unauthorized personnel accessing the campus have created multiple opportunities for various criminal activities.

All of these crimes are present because there is no proper security access control at the gates of the university. Hence, the people who usually commit these crimes in the university are believed to be non-students at the university without student cards to access to university. This has created many issues as the rise of crime in the university has increased and the security control on its own has become weak. Meaning that the use of tapping student cards to access the university is not working for us since any clever person who is not a student can easily steal one's student card and utilise it to access the campus or even ask a friend for their student card to use it. That, in turn, does not ensure that the person is indeed a student in the university and is allowed to enter the campus. Another issue is that the security guards do not really check every student who enters the campus, especially at gate 2. This creates a delay in checking every student's cards as more and more traffic is caused. For these reasons, the introduction and implementation of biometric devices in the University premises will assist in preventing the underlying issues from occurring.

Method

This is a conceptual paper which has adopted a literature-based methodology to critique the implementation of biometric devices in an attempt to ameliorate criminal activities. Through this methodology, data was collected using a desktop by utilizing databases such as Google Scholar, Sabinet, Science Direct, Research Gate and other website sources amongst others. The material (journal articles, books, internet sources) from these databases provided some conceptualization of biometric devices and assisted the researchers to link them to crime reduction. Hence, the aforementioned materials assisted the researchers to achieve the purpose of the paper.

A Thematic Content Analysis (TCA) was employed in analysing textual (qualitative or theoretical data. Anderson (2007) and Jaspal (2020) describe a TCA as a method of analysing qualitative data, which includes perusing through a set of information and looking for the meaning of data to establish themes. At times, it uses subjective experience as the core of making sense of the themes developed. The themes developed from immersing in the nitty-gritty of literature were elucidated by providing meanings, explanations, descriptions and justification thereof. These analyses were informed by different published materials and necessary suggestions and conclusions were drawn.

Review of Literature

This section unpacks and clarifies the themes that were developed. The purpose is to look into different debates from different scholars who have done similar studies pertaining to the use of biometrics in different field and areas of concern. However, the concern for this paper was to look on how the University of Limpopo could continue upgrading and using the biometrics at the entrances of the university to deter potential criminal activities. The section commences by describing the benefits of using biometrics in an attempt to stop criminal tendencies.

The Benefits of Biometric Systems in Crime Prevention

Biometric authentication is hailed as the future of security systems, significantly lowering the risk of security breaches and eliminating traditional security overhead. The key benefit of utilizing biometrics in crime prevention lies in its uniqueness, making it an ideal choice for authenticating individuals (Clark, 2022). Crime in South Africa is attributed to several factors, including high levels of poverty, inequality, unemployment, and social exclusion and the normalization of violence. Conversely, strict security enforcement and severe authentication tend to reduce crime rates (WPR, 2023). This is why the implementation of a biometric system must be introduced.

Biometric facial recognition system could assist in multiple ways to enhance security in all the senses (Smith & Miller, 2021). For instance, the fingerprint, iris, facial and voice recognition. Thus, a biometric facial recognition system could help to prevent fraud by better establishing identity (e.g., identify people using falsified driver's license) and would likely help to investigate serious crimes against persons, such as murder and assault, for instance, identifying unknown suspects via CCTV footage (Smith & Miller, 2021). The more recent turn to biometrics, the more there could be an apparent improvement in security and accuracy, as biometrics are unique and hard to fake or steal. Biometric systems will help keep the student's

safety at ease (Gray, 2019). This will assist in keeping the security tight at all the gates by offering a higher degree of security than conventional methods.

Not only will the biometric system assist in security purposes, however it will also monitor the attendance and time management of students and staff whenever they access the campus. In terms of any investigation undertaken by law enforcement, they can be able to utilise the biometric system to keep track of the user's activities. In terms of voice recognition, it is said to assist law enforcement in a number of use cases ranging from identifying terrorism suspects to perpetrators of criminal behaviours (Jansen, Dencik, & Javier, 2021).

Biometric Systems: Issues and Challenges

As technology permeates every facet of our existence, criminals are devising inventive methods for unlawful activities. Offenses like identity theft, hacking personal and corporate computers for confidential information, and cyber stalking are increasing. Government agencies grapple with the ongoing task of thwarting these crimes, prompting a shift toward the adoption of advanced biometric and forensic technologies (Clark, 2022). Biometric systems are thought to present challenges and issues for the use of a variety of these biometric systems on the campus. Since biometric systems differ, from voice recognition, facial recognition, fingerprint scanning to iris recognition. Each one of these types of biometric systems may have certain challenges in terms of implementing them in the campus (Marciano, 2019). Hence, we would have to implement one that will favour every student and staff, even those with disabilities. That is why, during the era of the COVID-19 pandemic, a range of different measures have been implemented worldwide to reduce the rate of new infections and to manage the pressure on national health services, including biometric systems (Gomez-Barrero et al., 2022).

Hygiene concerns have increased societal resistance to the use of touch-based sensors in biometric systems (Gomez-Barrero et al., 2022). The use of biometric systems in terms of the fingerprint sensors has currently proven to be unhygienic since it promotes the transmission of bacteria amongst individuals. Especially during the COVID-19 era. This particular measure presents a challenge as the majority refuse to utilise the fingerprint biometric system to prevent any type of bacteria or viruses from being infected. Additionally, the fingerprint biometric recognition degrades greatly when the finger is wet and wrinkled (Martinez-Martin, 2019). Therefore, there would be denied access due to physical distortion, i.e., finger cuts or injuries.

In terms of staff/student privacy, the idea that a photo can reveal private information is possible with facial recognition technology (Martinez-Martin, 2019). Since facial recognition uses a person's facial features to store the data as a face template. Any person within the university is able to see the student's information just by using the facial template to access their information. In this regard, it raises ethical questions about privacy, data protection and potential bias in the data and negative implications in association between the students and staff relationship. (Martinez-Martin, 2019). However, when the face is not well presented on the biometric system for scanning can degrade the performance of the system. For example, the facial recognition that is currently installed in the university gates has been functioning poorly, showing other students' facial images and mixing the students up. Also, wearing hats, shades or even

eyeglasses or even bad lighting and face rotation, such obstructions may change the operational conditions of the facial recognition.

Voice Recognition is a form of biometric data to verify a person or an unknown speaker that can be extracted from video platforms, social media, audio samples or even mobile phones (Jansen, Dencik, & Javier, 2021). The consequences of COVID-19 on voice recognition depend largely on the effect of face masks on the production of speech (Gomez-Barrero et al., 2022). Meaning that the face masks obstruct the lower parts of the face and present an obstacle to the usual transmission of speech sounds; they interfere with the air pressure variations emanating from the mouth and nose (Jansen et al., 2021). Since masks are designed with a particular fabric of layers that prevents the voice from being transmitted as it is raw, conversely, the voice is influenced by the type of textile or fabric used in the masks and the thickness.

Challenges may also arise in terms of the ability to affordability. If the campus will be able to afford the appropriate biometric system for the implementation, as these systems are very expensive and purchasing them might be costly if the budget of the university is tight. Cost is a key factor as end users and the other supporting organisations would need the biometric device to be as inexpensive as possible (Anderes et al., 2021).

Integration of a biometric system and security might also be a challenge for the security program and security department. The deployment of the biometric system might need to be taught to the security team on how it operates and what would be expected of them. The only issue is that some might find it hard to adapt to and learn the advanced technological system. This puts the security guards in a tight position, as well as the fact that fewer guards would be situated at the gates since the biometric system will be in place. Leading to the retrenchment of some security guards. Technically, the security guards' work will be replaced by biometric identification systems that will be implemented. Trying to get the best device that would work best for the university may require a lot in terms of cost and investment. Machine learning and deep learning algorithms typically require large amounts of data to successfully undergo the training phase (Anderes et al., 2021). In addition, biometric devices may require the collection of large amounts of data to adequately see if the device is feasible and to present to the target populations. Such can make biometric recognition technology challenging.

The Status-Quo of the University Entrances

As things stand at the current moment, the entrances of the university are in a vulnerable and precarious state to criminal activities. The pedestrian entrances are still not fixed, and the car entrances causes traffic congestion in the morning and in the afternoon. However, the new establishment of Gate 1 is expected to reduce traffic congestion amongst others. Hence, the presence of inadequate biometric systems on gates, including security systems and access control points, can give rise to numerous substantial hazards and security vulnerabilities. Clark (2022) indicates that the significance of biometric systems is growing in the identification of both known and suspected criminals. The utilization of advanced biometric technologies as a means to combat terrorist attacks and address criminal activities is experiencing an upward trend (Clark, 2022).

Ineffective biometric measures might enable unauthenticated individuals to enter restricted zones, potentially leading to theft, data breaches, or security breaches. As an illustration, when a fingerprint

recognition system is susceptible to manipulation, an individual could exploit it by employing a counterfeit fingerprint to gain access to a secure facility. Vulnerable biometric systems can be exploited through hacking, spoofing, or circumvention, leading to security breaches, data breaches, and the unauthorized acquisition of sensitive data. To illustrate, if a facial recognition system can be easily deceived by a photograph, an intruder could use a printed image to gain unauthorized access.

Examples of Biometric Systems in Different Organizations

Biometrics stands out as the optimal method for swiftly and securely verifying and validating individuals using distinct biological traits (Thales, 2023). In simple layman's terms, biometrics can be referred to as the most feasible method for reliably and swiftly identifying and confirming individuals by utilizing distinct biological attributes (Faundez-Zanuy, 2022). The objective is to gather a piece of biometric information from this individual, which could encompass a facial photograph, a voice recording, or a fingerprint image. In the past, biometric applications were primarily launched by governing bodies to manage military access and for the identification of individuals in legal and law enforcement contexts, all within a closely monitored legal and technological structure (Thales, 2023). In the present day, industries such as banking, retail, and mobile commerce show a significant interest in harnessing the advantages of biometrics. Of utmost significance, over the recent years, awareness and approval have surged, driven by the fact that millions of smartphone users now unlock their devices using either fingerprint scans or facial recognition. This is how technology, especially the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), shapes the current livelihoods.

American Airlines

Martin (2018) reports that American Airlines uses facial recognition as one of their securities, wherein the author writes that "your face is your passport" measures. Travelers are not required to use a passport or driver's license for identity verification. Instead, a camera captures a picture of the passenger and matches it against stored images in the Customs and Border Protection database. Trader (2014) indicates that facial recognition stands out in crime-solving due to its capability to swiftly and precisely identify suspects from extensive datasets, such as security camera footage. These systems are engineered to swiftly authenticate an identity within moments, surpassing the speed and precision of verification performed by airline personnel or federal screeners (Martin, 2018).

Barclays Biometric Technology

Pioneering a new approach within the financial sector, global banking giant Barclays was among the earliest to introduce a ground breaking feature: one-touch fingerprint access to banking services (Levo, 2021). Clark (2022) opines that the capability to identify latent fingerprints has become achievable and is regarded as one of the most valuable forms of physical evidence in contemporary criminal investigations. Trader (2014) agrees that biometric devices play a crucial role in crime resolution by enhancing fingerprint accuracy, connecting evidence from one crime scene to others, and identifying offenders through DNA evidence with greater precision. Over time, they (Barclays) expanded their biometric strategy to encompass voice-enabled biometrics as well. This innovative

biometric approach empowers Barclays' contact centre to recognize customers based on their initial spoken words during a call. This technology eliminates the need for conventional passwords, which are prone to being forgotten or lost. Instead, Barclays' voice recognition system analyses the distinct characteristics of each customer's voice to promptly verify their identity (Levo, 2021). This not only streamlines the authorization process for Barclays but also establishes a robust defence against fraudulent calls (Levo, 2021). This instance of voice-enabled biometric technology distinguishes customers by evaluating the unique physical attributes of their mouth and throat that contribute to their individual voice patterns. As a result, these voice patterns become inherently distinctive and extremely difficult to replicate.

Results and Discussion

One of the devices that use biometric are the cell phones, because some of the smart phones requires finger-prints or facial recognition to open them. This is done for safety and privacy measures. Institution or companies such as Zwipe, IDEMIA Group and NEC Global are some of the companies that use fingerprints and face recognition for either payment services or other security measures (Irwin, 2024). However, the aim of this paper was to critique, analyse and conceptualize the implementation of biometric devices in halting criminal activities in the University of Limpopo premises. It has relied on the use of existing literature to derive and strengthen its argument. It highlights that the biometric systems are unequivocally very imperative in curtailing criminal deeds, be it in the government, private sector and or the universities. The paper provided some scenarios wherein the biometrics are implemented to deter criminal issues. Although criminal syndicates find innovative ways to bypass the system of biometrics since it has demographic bias and algorithm unfairness, there is always room for improvement that should be undertaken to enhance the biometric systems. Of course, there are some challenges that stem from biometric systems. Such challenges include among others, breaches of the system. From a different angle, the challenges are not meant to weaken the biometric systems; however, they simply show that change is necessary and there is always a space for improvement. The current status of biometric devices in the University of Limpopo, especially at the main entrances (gates), is unfortunate because some are no longer working. Which means the safety and security of students and staff are at high risk.

Conclusion

This paper delved deeply into the discussions and on biometric systems to reduce criminal tendencies in the University of Limpopo, as well as the potential for existing biometric systems to enhance the University of Limpopo. However, in the COVID-19 age, the difficulties in guaranteeing trustworthy biometric recognition performance have increased significantly, necessitating new research initiatives. Hence, the paper indicated some of the advantages and disadvantages of using biometric devices. However, the disadvantages could be used as a way of improving the biometric devices, as the biometrics have the potential to impact the university with technological advancement. Therefore, this paper concludes that the implementation of biometric devices could assist the University of Limpopo in stopping criminal tendencies. It gives greater importance to continuing with authentication to ensure maximum security and safety. The conclusion made in this paper is

not necessarily final; however, it provides future researchers to explore the biometric systems and link them to different disciplines.

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